

Temperature-Dependent Study of EQE, V_{oc} , and Luminescence in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ Solar Cells

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Abstract

Halide double perovskites (HDP) constitute a distinct subclass of perovskites in which the single B-site metal cation is substituted by two different metal species, resulting in the general composition $\text{A}_2\text{BB}'\text{X}_6$. In this work, we investigate the optoelectronic behaviour of HDP solar cells under realistic operating conditions. Temperature-dependent spectral response measurements reveal a strongly varying Urbach energy. We also correlate photocurrent collection efficiency with photoluminescence quenching as a function of applied voltage and temperature.

Additionally, by measuring photoluminescence spectra and open-circuit voltage under both above-gap and sub-gap excitation and combining all this information, we suggest charge separation and recombination pathways in the device performance (see figure below).

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References

[1] F. Ebadi, K. Meraji, M. A. Torre Cachafeiro, F. Wolf, M. T. Sirtl, T. Bein, W. Tress, Effects of Tail States in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$

Figure: Optoelectrical processes occurring in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ perovskite solar cell. Reproduced with permission from Ebadi et al. [1], under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.